

Covid-19 /Part 2/

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I cannot recall any health issue that has so far provoked such strong cooperative action by professionals from all over the world and such a mobilization of collaboration that breaks protocols, licenses, authors' and copyrights, etc. In the urge to discover vaccine, medicine, methodology and secrets related to Covid-19 disease a cascade of publications and research activities of unpredictable scope has been triggered after the genome of the virus was unraveled and presented to the international scientific community. In this "primordial soup", from which the right decisions will emerge, we are looking for simple and clear things, and these are important. I would share them with questions and answers.

1. We are talking about an epidemically widespread virus. What is special about it is the insufficiently researched mode of transmission and the long period of time during which the carrier of the infection can transmit the virus. This remains "invisible" to those who have not yet fallen ill during the incubation period /7 days on average/ before the actual illness /healthy carriers/, as well as after the recovery, when the virus has not yet been eliminated. The large number of infected people worldwide and the expensive and insufficient tests are an obstacle for the science to determine exactly these periods and to observe the affected people.

2. For patients with initially not severe respiratory infections, who are outside the profile for free testing and cannot afford the PCR test because of its price, it is unclear whether they have Covid-19 or a known viral infection. The X-rays of such early cases are not informative. In this case, the simplest blood tests are those that indicate the new disease:

- increased neutrophils in normal leukocytes
- **slightly** increased ALT, CRP and urea

I emphasize that they are slightly increased, but it is obvious that this is a common "group behavior", which would be strange for other viruses.

3. The disease has two clearly defined forms - with shortness of breath and without shortness of breath, but for months the rule is that doctors wait until the patient gets worse to start treating him like in an action movie. The signs of aggravation are known, much is known about the forms of complications, but the simple values that indicate that the slightly ill patient will reach to the intensive care unit are not sought, examined and reported. If the patient is already diagnosed with Covid-19 in any form /tests, contacts, etc./ **low leukocytes with low lymphocytes and increased lactate dehydrogenase /LDH test with highest sensitivity and specificity/** are a clear sign that the patient must be prepared for shortness of breath. LDH shows that the barrier between the conflict and security zones in the lungs has been destroyed.

4. There needs to be a clear scheme of what part of the health care system will cover the undiagnosed early cases - patients are either paying for tests for Covid-19 themselves, impossible for many people, or they remain "hidden" and infect others. Without underestimating the efforts made so far, which have not been unsuccessful, we all see that the system is already "panting", and often wasting resources.

My recommendation is that peripheral medicine should be included in the diagnosis and treatment. We should not forget that 80% of Covid-19 sufferers are mild cases. Then points 2 and 3 will be very helpful for the bridges healthy<->ill and ill<->seriously-ill-with-shortness-of-breath.

5. I see many similarities between the HIV pandemic decades ago and the present one. The world was changed then. But just like now, there was no medicine and the method of transmission was unknown. The solution came with the tests that were accessible everywhere and an algorithm for specific behavior of the young people and the medical workers. Nowadays, nobody is surprised to find a condom in the teenager's bag or that the doctor is wearing gloves when taking blood.

If we want a relaxation of the quarantine measures, we must immediately create an algorithm for the normal work of the medical staff and an algorithm for human interaction. This is where I see the role of the media, in popularizing the regulations.